

Influence of Coomassie Brilliant Blue dye Doping on the Physical Properties of Hydrothermally Synthesized Cu-Sb-S Nanocomposites

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Abstract

This research examines the effects of Coomassie Brilliant Blue (CBB) incorporation on Cu-Sb-S nanocomposite thin films synthesized through hydrothermal methods. Samples were prepared with varying CBB concentrations (0, 0.01, 0.03, and 0.05 gm) and comprehensively known to have structural, morphological, optical, and electronic characteristics. XRD analysis successfully verified forming crystalline phases, with patterns showing characteristic peaks that evolved with increasing CBB content. Based on the X-ray diffraction results. The crystal formations of the products, Cu₃SbS₃, Cu₃SbS₄, and Na₂C₂O₄, are cubic, Tetragonal, and Monoclinic symmetry respectively. FE-SEM imaging revealed a uniform nanostructure distribution and controlled morphology across all compositions, confirming successful CBB integration into the host matrix. Optical characterization demonstrated systematic modifications in the transmission and absorption properties with an increasing CBB concentration, indicating effective band structure modification. The optical direct band gap values were proved UV-visible absorption to be 1.4, 1.5, 1.6 and 1.7 eV were estimated by Tauc plots for ratio (X= 0, 0.01, 0.03, 0.05 gm) respectively. Hall effect measurements revealed p-type semiconductor behavior throughout the composition range, with a notable trend of a decreasing carrier concentration from 9.53×10^{14} to 3.21×10^{14} cm⁻³ accompanied by a significant enhancement in carrier mobility from 4.231 to 27.654 cm²/V·s as the CBB content increased. These findings demonstrate a successful modification of the Cu-Sb-S system's optoelectronic properties through CBB incorporation, suggesting potential applications in photovoltaic devices and optoelectronic systems requiring high carrier mobility. It can also be used as a good absorbent layer in solar cells.

Keywords: *Nanocomposite thin films, Coomassie Brilliant Blue (CBB), Copper Antimony Sulfide, Hydrothermal synthesis, Optoelectronic properties, Surface morphology.*

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Introduction

The urgent global need for sustainable and efficient energy technologies has intensified research efforts in developing novel semiconductor materials for optoelectronic applications (Kareem, et al., 2022). Copper-based chalcogenide semiconductors are some that have emerged as promising candidates due to their earth-abundant constituents, favorable optoelectronic features and environmental compatibility (Atri, et al., 2020; Zhao, et al., 2024). Particularly, the copper-antimony-sulfide (Cu-Sb-S) system has attracted a great attention in recent years for its potential applications in photovoltaics, photodetectors, and other optoelectronic devices (Zhao, et al., 2019). The Cu-Sb-S system is a fascinating array of stable phases, mainly from Cu₃SbS₄ (famatinite) (Rahman, et al., 2020), CuSbS₂ (chalcostibite) (Kareem, et al., 2024), Cu₁₂Sb₄S₁₃ (tetrahedrite) (Trejo-Zamudio, et al., 2023), and Cu₃SbS₃ (skinnerite). These phases show remarkable p-type semiconducting features with tunable bandgaps between 0.5 and 2.0 eV and absorption coefficients of 10⁴ to 10⁵ cm⁻¹ (Hansen, & Mathiesen, 2018). Such features make them attractive for solar energy harvesting uses. One of the phases is Cu₃SbS₃ showing exceptional promise with its optimal bandgap of 1.5 eV and absorption coefficient of more than 10⁵ cm⁻¹, features aligning well with the theoretical requirements for high-efficiency solar cells (Zheng, et al., 2021). Yet, challenges hinder the practical implementation of Cu-Sb-S materials related to carrier mobility and electrical conductivity. Recent studies have focused on many strategies for enhancing these features, such as doping, surface modification, and compositional engineering (Chalapathi, et al., 2024). Incorporating organic dyes as surface modifiers is an innovative approach for tuning the optoelectronic features of semiconductor materials which remains relatively not explored for the Cu-Sb-S system. In this context, a novel approach by Coomassie Brilliant Blue R-250 (CBB, C₄₅H₄₄N₃NaO₇S₂) is a molecular modifier for Cu-Sb-S nanocomposites. CBB, traditionally employed as a protein stain in biochemistry, possesses unique electronic properties and a conjugated molecular structure that could potentially enhance charge transfer and light absorption characteristics when integrated with semiconductor materials (Lin, et al., 2019). The study has gotten the synthesis of Cu-Sb-S materials through various methods, including sputtering, chemical bath deposition, and hydrothermal techniques (Duan, et al., 2024) such as the solvothermal method provides a distinct advantage of controlling morphology, crystallinity, and phase composition. This enables the precise manipulation of reaction parameters for the optimization of the material features for specific uses (Lee, Pi, & Kim, 2020).

This work in particular studies the effect of CBB concentration (X = 0, 0.01, 0.03, 0.05 gm) on the structural, optical, and electronic features of Cu-Sb-S nanocomposites. Incorporating sodium oxalate (Na₂C₂O₄) as a reducing agent offers an additional control over dimension of the synthesis. It is the sodium salt of oxalic acid. It is a white, crystalline, odorless solid, with its well-defined redox properties and thermal stability up to 250-270°C, is crucial in controlling the growth and crystallization of the nanocomposites. The band gaps of the primary phases in this study, Cu₃SbS₃ (1.60-1.8 eV) and Cu₃SbS₄ (0.46-0.98 eV), span a range that is particularly interesting for optoelectronic applications (Zheng, et al., 2021). While previous studies have largely focused on synthesis methods and basic characterization of Cu-Sb-S systems, our work extends beyond these aspects to examine the fundamental interactions between the organic dye modifier and the semiconductor Nanocomposites performance. This research represents the first systematic investigation of CBB-modified Cu-Sb-S nanocomposites prepared via the solvothermal method. The study showed how the effect CBB incorporation influence the phase stability and crystallization behavior of Cu-Sb-S nanocomposites. and the mechanisms by which CBB modification affects the optical and electronic features of the material system, and the reducing properties of sodium oxalate interact with Cu-Sb-S Nanocomposites to influence the final material characteristics. Understanding these aspects is crucial to develop optimized synthesis protocols and

achieve better optoelectronic properties in Cu-Sb-S based devices. This study shows the possibility of opening new horizons to design efficient and low-cost materials for the next generation of optoelectronic uses. Recently, studies have shown a careful control of synthesis parameters and chemical modifications significantly impacting the performance of copper-based chalcogenides in many used. This thorough study establishes clear structure-property relationships and insights into the fundamental mechanisms which governs the observed feature improvement. Dealing with these fundamental aspects and focusing on practical applications make this work contribute to the field of sustainable semiconductor materials for optoelectronic devices. The findings have significant implications to develop next-generation solar cells, photodetectors, and other optoelectronic devices according to earth-abundant elements.

Practical Steps

Materials

This study develops a systematic hydrothermal synthesis for (CBB)X@(Cu-Sb-S) nanocomposite films using high-purity precursors. The primary materials included Copper dichloride double wetting $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99%, Xilong Ltd), Antimony trioxide Sb_2O_3 (99%, Xilong Ltd), thiourea ($\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$, 99%, Sigma-Aldrich), DMF (99.5%, Sigma-Aldrich), polyethylene glycol PEG (99%, Tianjin Guangfu), and Coomassie Brilliant Blue R-250 ($\text{C}_{45}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_3\text{NaO}_7\text{S}_2$, 98%, Sigma-Aldrich).

Preparation

This study prepares a novel synthesis method to prepare (CBB)X@(Cu-Sb-S) nanocomposite films. The starting materials are Copper dichloride double wetting ($\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1.17 g), Antimony trioxide (Sb_2O_3 , 1.14 g), thiourea ($\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$, 1.0 g), and polyethylene glycol (PEG, 0.5 g) as a binding agent. Coomassie Brilliant Blue R-250 ($\text{C}_{45}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_3\text{NaO}_7\text{S}_2$, CBB) was added in different ratios ($X = 0, 0.01, 0.03, 0.05$ g). The study dissolved precursors in 50 mL of deionized water and stirred over three hours, when the solution transformed into a dark blue foam. The resulting mixture was transferred to a 100 mL stainless steel autoclave followed by the subjection to hydrothermal treatment at 180°C for five hours. Upon the reaction period, the autoclave was left for cooling naturally to room temperature. We also collected blue-black precipitate and centrifuged at it at 3000 rpm for 20 minutes. The study then dried the separated product at 80°C for two hours, calcinated at 350°C for one hour to form Cu-Sb-S nanocomposites (Cu_3SbS_3 , Cu_3SbS_4) and sodium oxalate ($\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$) structures. The calcined powder was finely ground by agate mortars. To prepare thin films, dissolving 0.05 g of the composite material was in 5 mL of dimethyl formamide (DMF) and ultrasonically dispersed for two hours. The produced solution was deposited onto soda lime glass substrates by the drop-casting method to get uniform thin films.

Characterization and Analysis

The study analyses the crystallographic formation of the samples by X-ray diffraction (XRD) with an X'Pert PRO Diffractometer. The measurements were in Bragg-Brentano geometry by $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) at room temperature (25°C). The diffractometer at 40 kV and 30 mA is equipped with diffraction beam optics such as a fixed divergence slit (0.8709°), a 0.02 rad Soller slit, and a receiving slit of 0.100 mm diameter. For the minimization of peak broadening impacts, scans were done with a fixed step size of 0.05° for 1.5 seconds a step across the 2θ range of $10-80^\circ$. This study conducted a morphological characterization by Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) under vacuum conditions. It proved the elemental composition through Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) using a TESCAN MIRA3/RAITH LIS system. Optical features were investigated by UV-visible spectroscopy with a Shimadzu spectrophotometer. The comprehensive characterization detailed information about the crystalline

structures, particle size distribution, surface morphology, and optical features of the (CBB)X@(Cu-Sb-S) nanoparticle films. This synthesis approach is an effective method to produce high-quality nanocomposite films with a controlled morphology and tunable optical features making them potential for optoelectronic uses such solar cells, light-emitting diodes, and photodetectors. Hall effect measurements determined important electronic features including carrier mobility, carrier concentration, and the charge carriers (n-type or p-type). Different from simple conductivity measurements, not distinguishing hole from electron conduction, Hall effect analysis shows a decisive information about the dominant charge carriers to understand its electronic behavior and potential uses .

Results and Discussion

Structural Evaluation (X-Ray Analysis)

The material crystallinity measures the well-ordered atoms. These materials are regular atomic in shape but the amorphous disordered atomic. The first shows broad, diffuse peakss from the XRD methods. The X-ray diffraction quantify the size of individual crystalline domains in a material, like crystallite size. It is often less than the grain size as grains usually consist of many crystals. Grain size is the average diameter of every grain in a material. The nanoparticle inter planar spacing (d) can be calculated by Bragg's law (Kareem, et al., 2024; Kareem, et al., 2024):

$$2d \sin\theta = n\lambda \quad (1)$$

Here, θ is the diffraction angle, n an integer showing the reflection order ($n = 1, 2, 3\dots$), and λ is the X-ray wavelength (1.5406 Å).

The average crystallite sizes were calculated using the Scherrer equation (Theja, et al., 2022; Yang, et al., 2023):

$$D_{sh} = k\lambda/(\beta hkl \cos\theta) \quad (2)$$

Here D_{sh} represents the crystallite size, k is a shape factor (typically 0.9), λ is the X-ray wavelength, β the full width at diffraction peak half maximum (FWHM), and θ the diffraction angle .

The analysis revealed average crystal sizes of 27 nm for the Cu₃SbS₃ phase, 40 nm for the Cu₃SbS₄ phase, and 90 nm for the Na₂C₂O₄ phase, indicating the formation of nanocrystalline structures. The subsequent relationships are the lattice constants (a), the crystallographic orientation(d), and the degree of crystallinity (Miller index (hkl) planes). It is the mathematical representation of the crystallographic planes in three dimensions of Cubic, Tetragonal and Monoclinic phases, by the following relationship (Theja, et al., 2023; Khan, et al., 2022):

Cubic phase

$$\frac{1}{d^2_{hkl}} = \frac{h^2+k^2+l^2}{a^2} \quad (3)$$

Tetragonal phase

$$\frac{1}{d^2_{hkl}} = \frac{h^2+k^2}{a^2} + \frac{l^2}{c^2} \quad (4)$$

Monoclinic phase

$$\frac{1}{d^2_{hkl}} = \frac{1}{\sin^2 \beta} \left(\frac{h^2}{a^2} + \frac{k^2 \sin^2 \beta}{b^2} + \frac{l^2}{c^2} - \frac{2hl \cos \beta}{ac} \right) \quad (5)$$

The XRD analysis of the control sample in Figure 1(A1) (without CBB, x=0) revealed two distinct crystalline phases: 1. Cu₃SbS₃ exhibited a cubic crystal structure (space group I-43m) with characteristic diffraction peaks at 2θ values of 27.7° (422), 34.9° (620), 43.9° (732), and 45.9° (644), matching JCPDS card No: 01-075-1574. 2. Cu₃SbS₄ is a tetragonal crystal structure (space group I-42m) with peaks at 28.6° (213), 30.12° (220), 32.0° (301), and 45.2° (118), corresponding to JCPDS card No: 01-071-0555. Figure 1 (A2,A3,A4).

Figure 1 .XRD Diffraction Pattern of [(CBB)_x @ (Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites thin Films with Ratios (A1)_{x=0}, (A2)_{x=0.01}, (A3)_{x=0.03}, (A4)_{x=0.05} gm Produced by Hydrothermal Method

Upon incorporation of CBB (x = 0.01, 0.03, 0.05), a third crystalline phase emerged: 3. Na₂C₂O₄ (Jalal, & Aesa, 2023) , displayed a monoclinic crystal structure (space group P121/c1) with characteristic peaks at 21.9° (400), 42.2° (214), 48.1° (142), and 52.1° (234), matching JCPDS card No: 96-10-3691. The introduction of dye CBB significantly influenced the phase formation and

crystallization behavior of the nanocomposites. Notable observations include: the (422) peak at 27.6° showed the highest intensity, attributed to the Cu_3SbS_3 phase. Increasing CBB concentration (from $x = 0.01$ to 0.05) led to systematic changes in the relative peak intensities, indicating its role in modulating phase formation. The presence of $\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ in CBB-containing samples suggests a complex interaction between the Cu-Sb-S precursors and the CBB additive during hydrothermal synthesis.

Table 1. The Data on Structure and Physics [(CBB) $_x$ @(Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites Thin films with Ratios (A1) $_{x=0}$, (A2) $_{x=0.01}$, (A3) $_{x=0.03}$, (A4) $_{x=0.05}$ gm) Produced by Hydrothermal Method

2 θ (Deg.)STD	d_{hkl} Std.(Å)	2 θ (Deg.) EXP	d_{hkl} EXP.(Å)	FWHM (Deg.)	G.S (nm)	hkl	Crystal	Phase	card No.
							System		
22.0000	4.0370	21.9	4.0478	0.0970	83.5	400	Monoclinic	$\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	96-10-3691
27.6000	3.2293	27.7	3.2235	0.2560	32.0	422	Cubic	Cu_3SbS_3	01-075-1574
28.6600	3.1122	28.6	3.1175	0.1960	41.8	213	Tetragonal	Cu_3SbS_4	01-071-0555
30.12	2.9646	30.12	2.9645	0.18	45.7	220	Tetragonal	Cu_3SbS_4	01-071-0555
32.1000	2.7861	32.0	2.7988	0.1670	49.5	301	Tetragonal	Cu_3SbS_4	01-071-0555
35.1900	2.5482	34.9	2.5658	0.3120	26.7	620	Cubic	Cu_3SbS_3	01-075-1574
42.1000	2.1446	42.2	2.1421	0.0950	89.7	214	Monoclinic	$\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	96-10-3691
43.8100	2.0648	43.9	2.0616	0.3800	22.5	732	Cubic	Cu_3SbS_3	01-075-1574
45.21	2.0040	45.2	2.0040	0.2150	40.0	118	Tetragonal	Cu_3SbS_4	01-071-0555
45.8800	1.9763	45.9	1.9763	0.3500	24.7	644	Cubic	Cu_3SbS_3	01-075-1574
48.0000	1.8939	48.1	1.8912	0.0850	102.4	142	Monoclinic	$\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	96-10-3691
52.1300	1.7531	52.1	1.7531	0.0995	88.9	234	Monoclinic	$\text{Na}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	96-10-3691

The study systematically analyses the structural parameters, diffraction angles (2θ), FWHM, crystallite sizes, interplanar distances (d_{hkl}), and Miller indices (hkl), for all compositions. The results successfully formed multicomponent nanocomposites with well-defined crystalline phases, relative ratios tuned by changing the CBB concentration indicating the CBB additive effects on the phase formation and growth kinetics during the hydrothermal synthesis. This comprehensive structural analysis confirms the formation of complex nanocomposite systems with controllable phase composition and crystallinity, essential for optimizing their performance in various applications. Table 1 includes the structural parameters [(CBB) $_x$ @(Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites thin films (A1) $_{x=0}$, (A2) $_{x=0.01}$, (A3) $_{x=0.03}$, (A4) $_{x=0.05}$ gm) by hydrothermal method including the diffraction angle (2θ), full width at half maximum FWHM, crystallite size (C.S), intrinsic distance between crystal planes (d_{hkl}), and Millar indices (hkl).

Study of FE-SEM Analysis

FE-SEM is a versatile technique to evaluate the material morphology. Figure2(A-1,B-1) is the micrograph nanoparticles [(CBB) $_x$ @(Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites thin films with the ratio ($x=0$) is made from hydrothermal method with a magnification of strengths at 5KX, 100KX, 200KX.

Figure 2. FE-SEM for [(CBB)X @ (Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites Thin Films with Ratio (X=0) Produced by Hydrothermal Method, (A-1, and B-1) Surface Topography: (A-1) Inset: High -Resolution Image and Magnification, (B-1) Low -Resolution Image; (C-1) Study SEM Image (200 nm) by IMAGE-J Program (d-1) EDX Analysis

A uniform measuring conglomerates and a spherical-like shape with diameter of 53-37 nm appears. Also, it shows that the particles are nanoscale. The nanoparticles' precise microstructure was analyzed by EDSs (Zaki, et al., 2020; Zhang, et al., 2021). Figure2 (C-1) shows an analysis of the images by Image-J software. Figure2 (d-1) shows the EDS study of cubic and tetrahedrite composite nanoparticles. There were six peaks coinciding with two peaks for each copper, sulfur and antimony (Cu,S,Sb) peak. The program linked to the examination device measured the weight percentage ratios and the atomic percentage (Nefzi, Rabhi, & Kanzari, 2020). Generally, the SEM image offers a valuable insight into the physical and chemical particle features for understanding how the particle performs in different uses (Dutková, et al., 2023).

Figure 3(A-2, B-2) is the micrograph nanoparticles of [(CBB)_x@(Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites thin films with ratio (X=0.01) with diameter ranging from 36-110 nm is exhibited. The observed morphology and particle size distribution are typical of nanomaterials synthesized via hydrothermal methods. The agglomeration of nanoparticles is likely due to strong inter particle forces, for example van der Waals forces and electrostatic interactions. In addition, a porous surface can enhance the surface area of the nanoparticles, which may be beneficial for applications such as catalysis and sensing. In Figure 3 (C-2), the images were examined by the Image-J software. Figure 3 (d-2) is the EDS study of Cubic, Tetragonal and Monoclinic - Crystal system composite nanoparticles. There are two peaks for each of the copper (22.29), sulfur (24.10) and antimony (42.60) peaks. Yet, one peak appeared for each of the sodium (2.24), carbon (3.55) and oxygen (5.21) due to the addition of CBB producing a total of 100.00.

Figure 3. FE-SEM for [(CBB)X @ (Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites Thin Films with Ratio (X= 0.01) Produced by Hydrothermal Method (A-2, and B-2) Surface Topography: (A-2) Inset: High -Resolution Image and Magnification, (B-2) Low -Resolution Image; (C-2) Study SEM Image (200 nm) by IMAGE-J (d-2) EDX Analysis

Figure 4. FE-SEM for [(CBB)X @ (Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites Thin Films with Ratio (X=0.03) Produced by Hydrothermal Method.(A-3, and B-3) Surface Topography: (A-3) Inset: High -Resolution Image and Magnification, (B-3) Low -Resolution Image; (C-3) Study SEM Image (200 nm) by IMAGE-J (d-3) EDX Analysis

Figure 4(A-3,B-3) illustrates the micrograph nanoparticles of $[(\text{CBB})_x@(\text{Cu-Sb-S})]$ Nanocomposites thin films with ratio ($X=0.03$). with diameter ranging from 20-126 nm is exhibited. The SEM images reveal a heterogeneous morphology consisting of agglomerated nanoparticles with varying sizes and shapes. The particles exhibit a rough and porous surface, likely because of flaws and grain boundaries. In Figure 4 (C-3), Image-J software was used for image analysis while Figure 4 (d-3) for the EDS study of Cubic, Tetragonal and Monoclinic - Crystal system composite nanoparticles producing nine peaks similar to Figure 4 but with some differences. Copper, sulfur and antimony each has two peaks (20.23), (23.31) and 41.39) respectively. Yet, there is one peak for each of the sodium (3.13), carbon (5.11) and oxygen (6.82).

Figure 5. FE-SEM of $[(\text{CBB})_X @ (\text{Cu-Sb-S})]$ Nanocomposites Thin Films with Ratio ($X=0.05$) Produced by Hydrothermal Method. (A-4, and B-4) Surface Topography: (A-4) Inset: High -Resolution Image and Magnification, (B-4) Low -Resolution Image; (C-4) Study SEM Image (200 nm) by IMAGE-J (D-4) EDX Analysis

Figure 5(A-4,B-4) illustrates the micrograph nanoparticles of $[(\text{CBB})_x@(\text{Cu-Sb-S})]$ Nanocomposites thin films with ratio ($X=0.05$). with diameter ranging from 40-60 nm is exhibited. In Figure 5 (C-4) analyses the image by Image-J software. Figure 5 (d-4) is the EDS study of Cubic, Tetragonal and Monoclinic - Crystal system composite nanoparticles. Ten peaks are coincided with two peaks for each of the elements copper, and antimony (Cu,Sb) peaks. Three peaks for sulphur (S). Also, one peak for each of sodium, carbon and oxygen (Na,C,O). In general, all EDX images have a particle surface that is rough and porous possibly due to impurities and defects in the particle. The EDX analysis proved copper (Cu), sulfur (S), antimony (Sb), sodium (Na), carbon (C), and oxygen (O). The Na, C, and O indicates the successful incorporation of the CBB component into the nanocomposite structure. The introduction of CBB significantly influences particle size distribution, surface features, and elemental composition, suggesting potential pathways for optimizing material properties for specific applications. The observed surface roughness and porosity, combined with the varied elemental composition, indicate promising characteristics for applications in catalysis, sensing, and other surface-dependent processes.

The Optical Properties

The optical characteristics of dye [(CBB)X@(Cu-Sb-S)] nanocomposite thin films were comprehensively analyzed through transmission spectra, absorption coefficient measurements, and bandgap determination using Tauc plots. The analysis revealed systematic variations in optical properties with CBB concentration, providing insights into the material's potential for optoelectronic applications. Figure 6(A1,A2,A3,A4) shows the transmittance spectra of [(CBB)X@(Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites thin films with ratios X=0 , 0.01, 0.03, 0.05 gm) produced by hydrothermal method. The optical transmittance of thin films increases with increasing CBB ratios., This is particularly evident in the clear near-infrared of the spectrum. It is affected by surface morphology and defects at grain boundaries. It is also sensitive to changes in layer height and grain distribution. With increasing CBB content, a Blue-shift in the edge of absorption is observed indicating an increase in the optical bandgap of the material. This shift suggests fundamental modifications in the electronic structure of the material with CBB incorporation.

Figure 6. (A1,A2,A3,A4) The Variation of Transmission with Wavelength of [(CBB)X @(Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites Thin Films with CBB Ratios X=0 , 0.01, 0.03, 0.05 gm) Produced by Hydrothermal Method

Figure 7(B1,B2,B3.B4) shows the Absorption coefficient of [(CBB)_x @(Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites thin films with ratios X=0 , 0.01, 0.03, 0.05 gm) produced by hydrothermal method. the reduced absorption coefficient in the clear and near-infrared regions indicates that CBB incorporation reduces the light harvesting properties of the nanocomposite films.

A UV-visible spectrometer was used to examine optical property and the direct-allowed transition was applied. Figure 8(C1,C2,C3,C4) is the Tauc plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ and photon energy $h\nu$ (Ornelas-Acosta, et al., 2015).

Figure 7. (B1,B2,B3,B4) Absorption Coefficient as a Function of Wavelength for [(CBB)X@Cu-Sb-S] Nanocomposites Thin Films with CBB Ratios $x=0, 0.01, 0.03, 0.05$ gm Produced by Hydrothermal Method

The properties by UV-Vis spectrometer is the permissible direct transition. Figure 8 (C1, C2, C3, C4) is the Tauc diagram for $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ and the photon energy $h\nu$ (Mohammed, Aadim, & Ameen, 2018), according to Equation (6):

$$(\alpha h\nu)^{1/n} = A(h\nu - E_g) \quad (6)$$

Here α is the adsorption coefficient of the material, h is the Planck's constant, ν is the frequency of photon, n : nature of transition ($n=1/2$ for direct allowed transitions).

In addition, a is a proportionality constant, and E_g the optical band gap energy. The linear area of the Tauc plots, used to determine the bandgap, becomes less pronounced with increasing CBB content. This may indicate additional electronic transitions or broadening of the band edges. The linear broadening in the Tauc plots may be due to the presence of defects or disorder in the material, which can introduce additional electronic states and broaden the energy distribution of the carriers. Extrapolating the linear portion curve to zero absorption is the direct E_g , (Rath, et al., 2015). This study directs the direct energy gap values (E_g) of [(CBB)X@Cu-Sb-S].

Figure 8. (C1,C2,C3,C4) The Variation of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ Versus Photon energy ($h\nu$) for [(CBB)X@Cu-Sb-S] Nanocomposites Thin Films with CBB Ratios $X=0, 0.01, 0.03, 0.05$ gm) Produced by Hydrothermal Method

Nanocomposites thin films with CBB ratios $X=0, 0.01, 0.03, 0.05$ gm equal (1.4,1.5, 1.6 and 1.7 eV) respectively. The observed blue-shift in the optical bandgap can be attributed to the quantum confinement effect. The drop in the size of the nanocrystals increases the CBB content, the energy levels of the electrons and holes become quantized, increasing the bandgap energy. Naturally, many sizes and morphologies of crystalline phase are a key in the energy gap. According to this band gap energy, this material has possible uses for solar energy absorbers (Kareem, et al., 2025). The comprehensive optical characterization reveals that the [(CBB)X@Cu-Sb-S] nanocomposite system offers a significant potential for optoelectronic applications, particularly in solar energy conversion devices. The ability to tune optical properties through CBB concentration provides a valuable tool for materials engineering in this system.

Hall Effect

From the this Effect measurements, the conductivity σ , carrier concentration nH , Hall coefficient RH and carrier mobility μH values were calculated and listed in Table2. The positive Hall coefficient sign shows that RH the conductivity nature of all films is p-type. This means that the majority carriers are holes (Rouchdi, et al., 2017).

Table 2. Hall Measurements for [(CBB)X @(Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites Thin Films with CBB Ratios $x=0, 0.01, 0.03, 0.05$ gm) Produced by Hydrothermal Method

CBB%	n_H (cm) ⁻³	R_H (cm ⁻³ C ⁻¹)	σ (Ω .cm) ⁻¹	μ_H (cm ² /v.sec)	Type
0	9.53483E+14	6545	18.24	4.231	p
0.01	8.33921E+14	7484	14.22	6.1023	p
0.03	6.33921E+14	15678	10.8	13.6522	p
0.05	3.21044E+14	19441	9.32	27.6540	p

Figure 9. The Variation of Conductivity σ , Carrier Concentration n_H , Carrier Mobility μ_H and Hall Coefficient R_H of [(CBB)X @(Cu-Sb-S)] Nanocomposites Thin Films with CBB ratios $x=0, 0.01, 0.03, 0.05$ gm) Produced by Hydrothermal Method

Figure 9 (A) shows that the value of conductivity σ decreased from 18.24 (Ω .cm)⁻¹ at 0% CBB to 9.32 (Ω .cm)⁻¹ at 0.05 gm CBB with the increasing CBB ratios, Falling. This can be attributed to the insulating nature of the CBB component, and likely due to the reduced carrier concentration and increased scattering of charge carriers by the CBB inclusions. Figure 9 (b) reveals that the value of carrier concentration n_H also decreases from 9.53×10^{14} cm⁻³ to 3.21×10^{14} cm⁻³ with increasing CBB content. This significant decrease (about 66%) suggests that the CBB inclusions act as effective carrier traps, decreasing the free charge carriers available for conduction. Figure 9 (c) explains that the value of Carrier Mobility (μ_H): Interestingly, while other parameters show decreasing trends and the carrier mobility exhibits a significant increase with higher CBB content, rising from 4.231 cm²/V·s to 27.654 cm²/V·s – an approximately 6.5-fold increase. This enhancement in mobility is particularly important and due to better crystallinity of the material, potentially reduced carrier-carrier scattering due to lower carrier concentration and modified

electronic structure at the CBB-semiconductor interfaces. Figure 9 (d) is the Hall coefficient RH that demonstrates a positive value across all samples, definitively indicating p-type semiconduction where holes are the majority charge carriers. The RH value increases substantially from 6,545 $\text{cm}^{-3}\text{C}^{-1}$ to 19,441 $\text{cm}^{-3}\text{C}^{-1}$ with increasing CBB content, which confirms the observed decrease in carrier concentration (since RH has a negative relation to carrier concentration).

The overall trends suggest that CBB incorporation significantly modifies the electronic features of the Cu-Sb-S nanocomposite films. The trade-off between decreased conductivity and increased carrier mobility could be particularly interesting for applications where high mobility is more critical than high conductivity, such as in certain sensor or electronic devices. The consistent p-type behavior across all samples indicates that the fundamental semiconductor character of the material is preserved despite the CBB modifications.

Conclusions

Dye Coomassie Brilliant Blue (CBB) Integration into Cu-Sb-S nanocomposite thin films via hydrothermal synthesis has resulted in significant property modifications. XRD analysis demonstrated preserved crystalline structure across all CBB concentrations, while FE-SEM imaging confirmed uniform nanostructure formation and distribution. The optical properties exhibited systematic evolution with increasing CBB content, indicating successful electronic structure modification. The most significant finding was the substantial enhancement in carrier mobility, showing a 6.5-fold increase (4.231 to 27.654 $\text{cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$) despite decreased carrier concentration (9.53×10^{14} to 3.21×10^{14} cm^{-3}). This inverse relationship suggests improved charge transport mechanisms within the modified structures. The maintenance of p-type semiconductor behavior across all compositions, coupled with systematically increasing Hall coefficients, confirms the controlled modification of electronic properties through CBB incorporation. The observed enhancement in carrier mobility while preserving semiconductor characteristics presents a promising avenue for applications in high-performance optoelectronic devices. These results demonstrate that CBB incorporation serves as an effective method for tuning the optoelectronic properties of Cu-Sb-S nanocomposites. The combination of improved mobility and controlled electronic properties suggests potential applications in advanced electronic devices, particularly where high carrier mobility is essential for optimal performance, such as in high-speed electronic circuits and advanced sensing applications. In addition, our results suggest that such films would be useful as an absorber layer in solar cells applications.

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